

Research Paper

Social Security and Poverty Reduction in Onelga, Rivers State.

Akujuru Chukwunonye Abovu, Ph.D

Mobile: 08037450542 E-Mail: chukwunonye.akujuru1@ust.edu.ng

Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt.

Akiri Samuel

Mobile: 08148244992 E-Mail: akirisamuel2018@gmail.com

Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt.

Georgewill Azubuiké, JP

georgewillazubuiké@gmail.com

Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt.

Corresponding Author: Akujuru Chukwunonye Abovu, Ph.D

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ABSTRACT: This study focuses on social security and poverty reduction in ONELGA, Rivers State. The study was induced by the level of poverty prevalence among the rural dwellers in ONELGA community despite the abundance of natural resources, complimented by the efforts made by the government to improve the living condition of the people in the rural areas. It was geared toward finding out whether implementation of social security programs and projects in the area can significantly improve the lives and standard of living of people in ONELGA. Data collected for this study is basically secondary data. It was observed that effective implementation of social security programs and projects will help to reduce poverty in ONELGA. It was then recommended that the state government should resuscitate and continue the free school bus programme, the free medical care programme for the continued benefits of the citizens and the state. The state-owned syringe manufacturing company should also be rehabilitated to help in the areas of employee's generation and poverty reduction and there should also be a positive re-orientation on social security among

Keywords: social security, poverty reduction, community development projects and programs.

I. Introduction

Social security is a type of social insurance scheme established to protect society's most vulnerable members from the uncertainties of daily living. The International Labour Organisation (ILO) Conventions and United Nations (UN) instrument have designated Social security as a basic human right because it ensures greater access to health care and a minimally acceptable standard of living, particularly for the elderly, the unemployed, the sick, pregnant women, and for vulnerable children (ILO, 2001). Both childhood and old age have been shown to be barriers to output, especially for the elderly whose capacity to produce declines with age. Social security is necessary and desirable because elderly people frequently lose their jobs and sources of income, while orphans and other vulnerable youngsters frequently need care and protection. Before there were institutional social security programmes, children, families, communities, and society were responsible for providing food, clothing, and shelter to the elderly and other vulnerable people (Ekpenyong, Onyeneonye et al. 1986). The need for a formal social security architecture, however, arises as industrialization gains traction in the economy, family sizes start to shrink, and family members

start to disperse in search of greener pasture. This collective measure is meant to ensure that members of a given society do not lack the necessary income to meet basic needs and maintain a standard of living that is consistent with international best practises. (1986; Epkeyong and Oyeneonye). More people's reliance on wage employment has contributed to the changes in social security's nature and character that are already apparent. The Nigerian government offers schemes like free medical care, social rehabilitation programmes, and residences for various population groups as additional social insurance against old age poverty and desperation. With the passage of the Pension Ordinance in 1957, Nigeria's pension programme received legal support for the first time. A number of improvements to the programme later, the programme is presently governed by the Pension Act of 2004. As a concept, social security goes beyond pensions to embrace all government initiatives, services, and policies that support the most vulnerable members of society. Pension plans can be either contributory or noncontributory. Contributory pension plans primarily redistribute money that has previously been withheld from an employee while they were still in the workforce in preparation for retirement. The non-contributory social security programme, however, receives funding directly from the government. Since access to the fund does not result from pre-working or a contribution to the scheme, the noncontributory pension system better matches our definition of social security for the most vulnerable in society. Every vulnerable person is anticipated to get benefits from the noncontributory social security system, unless it is particularly intended just for a particular group of people, such as children or the elderly. Government all over the world are in the business of providing social security protections for their citizens. In Rivers State the PAY-AS-YOU-GO contributory pension scheme, is part of the state government social security programme targeted at the elderly in the society, specifically those that have retired from government services. Therefore, this study is aimed at investigating the availability of institution that provides social security services for children in Rivers State and how it has contributed to poverty reduction in the state. This study first aims to determine the availability, effectiveness, and efficacy of the programme in ameliorating and/or reducing the suffering of the less privileged and the challenges facing the programme. These policies and programmes of the government that are intended to alleviate the suffering of the society's vulnerable category (the poor children) are the subject of this research work. In more developed cultures, people are expected to obtain social security numbers to access facilities; but, in poor nations like Nigeria, eligibility for various government-sponsored social security programmes is typically based on age and gender. The state of Rivers, which is frequently referred to as a microcosm of Nigeria, has experienced its fair share of the extreme poverty that is evident throughout the nation.

Therefore, the political leadership must have a clearly expressed viewpoint on social security programmes. According to Ali (2013), leadership failure and the inability to ensure human security as a kind of social welfare based on the values of equity, freedom, and justice are to blame for the rising challenges of insecurity and other socio-economic development indices. According to Norton, et al. (2001), a comprehensive social security system is unlikely to succeed without the help of technocrats. Beyond social welfare organisations, other government entities must play a major role in the formulation of public policy. Political savvy is necessary in developing nations to win over the public to tax-funded social security and protection for vulnerable groups.

II. Statement of Problem

The level of social security protection programmes for the population has been criticised by researchers in the field, particularly as it relates to the poor and other vulnerable members of society who, due to their age, lack the ability or legal right to engage in productive work to help themselves. Musovo (2007), cited in Poroma, et al. (2018), suggested that a variety of factors, such as poverty, a lack of education, insufficient regulations to prohibit child employment, illiteracy, child poverty, broken marriages, and a lack of social safety nets, might be used as justifications for child labour. They claimed that this has an impact on the socioeconomic growth of the state and that as a result, well-thought-out policies and programmes for the care of children are required, as well as improved access to social services to ensure better social conditions that would eradicate poverty. Investigating the entire impact of social security schemes and policies is the focus of this work.

III. Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To identify the nature of social security structure in Rivers State.
2. To ascertain the existence of social security programmes in Rivers State.
3. Examine how social security structure/programme contributed to poverty reduction in Ogba Egbema Ndoni LGA.

Research Questions:

In carrying out this research work we shall attempt to provide answers to the following questions:

1. what is the nature of social security structure in Rivers State?
2. is there any existence of social security programmes in Rivers State?
3. How has social security structure/programme contributed to poverty reduction in Ogba Egbema Ndoni LGA?

IV. Conceptual Clarification

Social Security

In the literature now in print (Nwabueze, 1989; Canagarajah & Sethuraman, 2001; ILO, 2001; Hummelsheim, Hirtenlehner, Jackson, & Oberwittler, 2011), the idea of social security has been prominently discussed. This is mostly due to its effects on socioeconomic development, general human well-being, and the safety or security of any community. Second, and probably more significantly, there are obvious misunderstandings of the idea held by governments, organisations, groups, and people, particularly in emerging cultures in Africa. In fact, it appears that such misunderstandings that emphasise or attempt to prioritise territorial safety against outsiders have lessened the importance of social security in several developing cultures, particularly Nigeria. This appears to have either slowed down or significantly decreased public awareness of social security as a requirement for group safety. The definition of social security as an arrangement by which a government provides basic assistance in terms of money and facilities to those members who are unable for one reason or another to provide for themselves appears to be agreed upon by academics (Nwabueze, 1989; Eboh, 2009; Nwafor, 2009; Waid, 2012). Consequently, Nwabueze (1989) in-depth argued that social security is about the social protection, organised collective protection of the individual against the economic consequences—loss or suspension of income, poverty, want, destitution, etc.—arising from certain social risks of life, namely: (a) Sicknes, "i.e.," a morbid condition due to non-occupational disease or injury that causes temporary or short-term disability;

abstention from work; (b) Maternity, which necessitates absence from work during the predetermined time periods before and after childbirth; (c) Invalidity, which refers to permanent or long-lasting and more-or-less total disablement as a result of non-occupational injury or disease; (d) Death as a result of non-occupational injury or disease; (e) Old Age, which refers to reaching a certain age, which varies from country to country (f) Workplace injury or disease that results in death or a temporary or permanent inability to perform one's job; (g) Loss of employment for a person who, despite being capable of and available for regular employment in one or more occupations, is unable to do so. Waid (2012:3) claims that "social security is a federal programme designed to protect individuals and their families from loss of earnings due to retirement, disability, or death". He added that Social Security has been a crucial tool for advancing the welfare of those who are no longer able to work. Social security offers a special framework for addressing problems and accomplishing the many objectives that every society aspires to. According to Nwafor (2009), "achieving a variety of goals, such as efficiency, equity, economic growth, macroeconomic stability, and full employment, among others, might boost economic viability. For him, the only source that offers a special opportunity to achieve these aims is social security. While most governments in established nations like the United States, Britain, and France, etc., have created long-lasting social security systems, most developing societies, particularly in Africa and Nigeria, have not yet begun. In the latter scenario, social security is not viewed as a fundamental human right but rather as a set of voluntary welfare services offered by the government out of goodwill. Although it is understood that not all societies can afford the same level of social security, it is crucial to keep in mind that it is inhumane to live and work anywhere without social protection that can withstand the ongoing insecurity posing a threat

to an individual's or a family's physical and mental well-being (see ILO, 2001). Not the informalization of the formal labour market, but rather the rapid growth of what is known as the "informal" economy or sector, which implied low income and poor working conditions, may be a more significant factor behind the renewed concern for social protection, especially in developing countries (Canagarajah & Sethuraman, 2001). The Pension Reform Act was passed in Nigeria in 2004, making it a good example of a developing society where social instability appears to be quite high but where there hasn't been a lot of serious effort to change things. In fact, the act may have helped to improve social security policies. We stress that, given that social security issues in Nigeria have reached crisis proportions, even a minimal contribution is insignificant.

Social security entails a variety of intricate procedures and initiatives that focus on the society as a whole. Every employee is protected under the new Pension Act. Additionally, it has not yet been successfully implemented in the private sector. Numerous unemployed people in Nigeria therefore have little possibility of being protected. The implication is that the vast task social security is mandated to complete may not be meaningfully addressed by the Pension Act. Social security appears to be more all-inclusive; it takes a broad view of society. It "traverses the cross-section of society, including the employed, unemployed, aged, physically challenged persons, poor and vulnerable persons, healthy and unhealthy persons" (Eboh, 2009:10). Hummelsheim, et al. (2011) state that "social protection consists of diverse policies and programmes designed to lessen people's exposure to risks and improve their capacity to protect themselves against hazards and loss of income in order to reduce poverty and vulnerability." It covers a wide range of topics related to helping individuals, families, and groups and, in general, cuts across all groups, including those in or out of the workforce at any one time.

Social Security and Poverty Reduction

The legendary Nelson Mandela of South Africa spoke at the "Make Poverty History" campaign in London in February 2003, reinvigorating calls for a global commitment to the eradication of poverty worldwide. Like slavery and apartheid, poverty is not a natural state, said Mandela. "It is a man-made problem that can be solved and eliminated by human action." He imagined a future without poverty, echoing Condurreet's thesis in the aftermath of the French Revolution (Stedman Jones, 2004). Condurreet wrote in 1793 of an impending campaign to combat global disparities, "that everything tells us that we are now close upon one of the great revolutions of the human race." The terms "poverty reduction" and "international finance" have become key slogans in the international development agenda, both in terms of development goals and new instruments in the international development agenda (Guobao, 2000). Poverty does not mean the same thing to everyone; the difficulty in defining poverty originates from the various points of view on the matter. This is because what one person considers to be poor may not be considered to be poor by another. Aside from that, deciding where to draw the line between poor and non-poor is always tough. Obaelu and Uffort (2007). Governments around the world have found it convenient to measure poverty in a way that matches their own conditions and focus. However, there appears to be a consensus among social scientists in measuring poverty as either a lack of money or an inadequacy of it in terms of income and expenditure needs, with an argument that the emphasis on money is predicated on the fact that insufficient income or lack of money are measurable and an immediate concern of all. According to the United Nations Statistical Audit (UNSA 2005), the first definition of poverty was the inability to obtain adequate food and other basic necessities. World Bank Report (1990) and Aigbokham (2000) established poverty as the inability to achieve a certain minimal standard of living. Poverty is defined by Aluko (1975), as a lack of command over basic consumption needs, in other words, the poor has an insufficient level of consumption, resulting in insufficient food, clothing, and shelter, as well as a lack of certain capacity(s), such as the ability to participate in society with dignity. In reference to this, Kamanou (2005) stated that poverty is often connected with a lack of some of life's essential needs, such as food, shelter, clothes, basic education, primary healthcare, and security, which he noted determines and defines standard of living.

The 1995 Copenhagen Declaration provided a more comprehensive definition of poverty as follows: From the foregoing, it is reasonable to conclude that poverty is both an economic and a social issue that manifests itself in numerous ways. It is also clear from the preceding that, regardless of any definition or coloration given to the concept of poverty, it remains the lack or insufficiency of some essential element of life, and it further reduces man's confidence and dignity, as well as the victim's social and psychological prestige (Adefo, 2006; Anger 2010). Soyombo (1987) agreed with other scholars in his spirited endeavour

to define poverty that the concept is illusive and difficult to measure or define. He acknowledged that different people interpret the concept differently. In the future, he continued, while economists think of poverty in global terms, sociologists and psychologists think of it in relative or comparative terms. According to Sachs (2005), Nweze and Ojowu (2002), poverty can be divided into three categories: (a) absolute poverty, (b) relative poverty, and (c) subjective poverty. Absolute poverty is defined by the basic human necessities required to maintain bodily efficiency. Haralambos and Health, 1980; Kuper and Kuper, 1996. Individuals, families, and communities in absolute poverty are those who are unable to afford the resources, including actual income, required to maintain a basic quality of life and human well-being. Sachs 2005, In order to create poverty lines (the upper poverty line, the lower poverty line, and the extremely poor category, Ali Akpajiak divided poverty into the poor and the core or extremely poor. Those whose income falls below the upper poverty line but above the lower poverty line are classified as poor, while those whose income falls below the lower poverty line are classified as the extremely poor. All people who are on the border of absolute poverty run the danger of developing chronic illnesses, inadequate nutrition, inadequate education, a short life expectancy, squalor, and physical and mental retardation. When an individual's or a household's income is lower than the average income of the people in a given society, it is said to be in relative poverty. This indicates that people who live in relative poverty have resources that are significantly less than those of other average people or households. As a result, they are unable to participate in activities and patterns of living that are considered socially acceptable. This situation is supported by comparisons with one or more measures of the current standard of living (Nweze 2002). There appears to be general agreement among people who share certain characteristics, such as (a) low education (b) unstable employment (c) low status jobs (d) low and unstable income (e) poor housing (f) large families (g) lack of savings (h) constant struggle for survival (i) little and/or poor material possession, despite the myriad of challenges associated with finding an acceptable definition and measurement for poverty. According to Soyombo (1982: p. 28), contrary to the reasonable expectation that poverty would make people more austere and prudent in their spending and lifestyle, one finds that the poor's way of life is marked by absurd behaviour that serves as a barrier to success and upward mobility, such as poor financial management, extravagant, conspicuous living, alcoholism, drug addiction, recklessness, sexual promiscuity, gambling, and pool betting. Because of the complexities linked with the complicated web with which poverty is weaved, it is difficult to distinguish between the source and impact of poverty. Given the aforementioned scenario, poverty is perceived as a result of the circumstances or as a result of the conditions precipitating poverty. Theoretical the reduction or obstruction of a normal cultural contact between an individual or group of individuals and the rest of society is referred to as social deprivation.

According to Samuel stuffer (1962), social deprivation is included in the general rubric of relative deprivation theory. The term social deprivation, though slightly ambiguous, includes a broad network of related factors that contribute to social exclusion, such as poverty, poor education, and low social economic status of the affected individual. Byrne (1999) defines social exclusion as "all the various ways in which people can be disadvantaged in society," namely the incapacity to fully engage in society. Townsend (1979) went on to argue that poverty encompassed more than just a lack of tangible possessions. He emphasised that poverty should be defined in relation to the standard of living in a specific society at a specific moment. According to Townsend, the concept of relative deprivation should be considered in terms of the resources accessible to an individual and household. Relative deprivation, according to Pethgrew (1967), Smith (2001), has become a key social science topic since social judgements are affected not just by absolute standards, but also by social comparisons. A child who is socially deprived, excluded, or has experienced abusive caretaking during the critical period of childhood is more likely to struggle with normal social behaviours and may even show resistance to rehabilitation later in life if given the opportunity or exposure to appropriate stimuli. As a result of this chain of events, the individual may be unable to make a meaningful contribution to the socioeconomic growth of her or his society or surroundings. According to Pierson (2012), if a child is denied access to social supports, that child is more likely to grow up poor and uneducated. The inability to receive a fair share of economic resources will fuel the increased gap in socioeconomic status, and this low status will further become social deprivation due to a lack of access and opportunity to have a political voice, which will limit his involvement and participation in the community. Lack of engagement in the work market and access to essential services further restrict inclusion of social relations, which include activities like social gatherings and assistance

during difficult times. Social society provides vulnerable children with this crucial part of assistance when they need to move around, which supports the suitability of this theory for the study.

Social Security Programmes for Children and Poverty Reduction in Rivers State

In the cause of this research the researcher identified four major components of the Rivers State Government Social security institutional programmes for children. These institutions and programmes includes the Port Harcourt Children's Home, the Remand Home Borikiri, the free school bus, free medicals and the Family Welfare Programme of the State Ministry of Social Welfare. The Children's Home is a home specially meant to accommodate orphans and vulnerable children in the society for care and protection. Officials of the state Welfare Ministry, identifies vulnerable children in the society for care and protection, enroll them at the home, monitor their progress, give them out for adoption , reunite with family or graduate them at the appropriate time. The Remand Home on the other hand, takes care of juvenile cases, taking into custody and initiating the process of counseling and rehabilitation for a period between three (3) to six (6) months for children between the ages of 7 and 17 who are either beyond parental control or have committed criminal offences. The family welfare unit on the other hand, handles family/ marital issues bothering on child custody and child welfare, while the Free School Bus programme carter for the transportation of all children of school age. As stated earlier, the Rivers State Government social security Programmes are ran through the ministries of Health, Education and Social Welfare. The Ministry of Social Welfare oversees the activities of the Port Harcourt Children's Home Borikiri, the Remand Home Borikiri, and the Family Welfare Unit of the ministry, The Ministry of Education on the other hand oversees the Free School Bus Programme Using statistical data, and table this study shall show how Government social security programmes for children has contributed to poverty reduction in the state. Between the year 2000 when the Free Medical Care Programme was first initiated and 2015 when it was suspended, the table above shows that the number of institutions that provided the services, increase from the initial 36 health institution to one hundred and seventy one (171) this was as a result of two (2) Memorandum of Understanding signed in 2011 and 2013 to engage the services of private medical facilities. Within the fourteen years duration of the programme, the table also shows that a total number of seven hundred and thirty thousand, five hundred and thirty-five (730, 535) medical cases of different categories were handled by the Free Medical Care Programme. Out of this number, four hundred and thirty-three thousand, seven hundred and seventy-four (433, 774) were children and natal registration/birth cases, while the rest were adult medical cases. Out of this number, four hundred and twenty five thousand (425,000) cases were directly handled in government owned health facilities across the state, while eight thousand six hundred and twelve (8, 612) were handled in partner private medical facilities, and another one hundred and sixty two (162) cases involving children were referred overseas for further medical treatments.

Because health care is such an expensive venture, it therefore means that deteriorating health and chronic illnesses are a beacon to poverty. The provision of free medical care for children by the state government has aided in more ways than one in the reduction of abject poverty in the state. With the introduction of the Free Medical Care Programme, the government have succeeded in lifted the burden of health care cost from parent whose child/children are eligible for the free medical care programme, who can now channel the fund saved by accessing the free medical care programme to other areas of need. The medical treatment given to the aforesaid four hundred and thirty three thousand, seven hundred and seventy four (433, 774) children and expectants mothers within the period of this study if translated in to money terms run into millions of Naira, a cost if not for the free medical programme would have been burn by the parents of the children, which in turn would increase their financial burden and poverty levels. The lifting of this financial burden from the parents therefore have helped in poverty reductions, as most parents in an attempt to provide good medical treatment for their children could have sank deeper into poverty or even abject poverty. Secondly, the staffs at the private hospitals across the state that partnered with the government for the delivery of free medical care are sure of adequate and prompt salary payment and some of the hospital may have engaged the services of more staffs by way of employment thereby helping them earn a living and reducing their poverty levels. Finally, following the inception and success of the Free Medical Care Programme, the Sir Dr Peter Odili DIRI, Benjamin B. & Eyinda O. OWABIA Year Number of institutions Total No of cases Govt. Hospital Private Hospital Oversees Adult Children Adult Children Adult Children Adult Children 2000 36 296,761 433, 774 275, 000 425,000 21, 388 8, 612 373 162 2015 171 171 730, 535 700, 000 30, 000 535 July / 120 www.socialsciencereview.net administration is 2001

initiated the construction of Syringe manufacturing company in Port Harcourt. The Pan African Health Foundation Auto-Disable syringe manufacturing plants have the capacity to produce one billion needles, 120 million infusion solutions annually, and had in her employment 250 staffs. Without the Free Medical Care Programme, the need may never have arisen for the establishment of a company that manufactures medical allied products. This company now has in her pay roll 250 staff, who earns salaries from working in that establishment, these people who are now employed and working at deferent levels in the establishment may still be unemployed and poor without the existence of the company. Conversely, the Rivers State Ministry of Education operated the government Free School Bus Programme between 1999-2015. The ministry has a fleet of twenty-three (23) sixty (60) seater air-conditioned buses plying four (4) routes within the Port Harcourt metropolis. The Free School Bus Programme had under its employment twenty seven (27) drivers and forty six (46) driver assistants (conductors).whose economic livelihoods were derived from the continued operation of the Free School Bus Programme, the monthly pay they received had helped to lift them and their families from poverty in the mean. The School Bus whose operations were restricted to the Port Harcourt metropolis covering the Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas, plied five routs within the city, including Isaac Boro Park to Oil Mill junction, covering the entire length of Aba road, Garrison junction to slaughter, the Trans Amadi, Garrison to Rumuomasi, Park to Rumuokoro through Ikwerre road and Park to Borikiri through Lagos Bus Stop. The Train service of the Free School Bus Programme, operates between Oyigbo and Port Harcourt with a final stop at the Port Harcourt Train station Port Harcourt township. One the average the Free School Buses inclusive of the train services under the scheme, transport over Sixteen thousand, seven hundred and forty-six school children on a daily basis, (16,746). Each of these children could have paid an average transport fare of about one hundred and fifty (N150.00) naira to and from school daily. The availability of the free buses has saved each parent an average amount of three thousand naira (N300.00) per child per day. Parents who had more than one child of school age would have served more money. Conversely, a civil servant parent who earns eighteen thousand-naira N30,000 minimum wage, with three (3) school age children would have spent half of his monthly salary on transportation alone, which would have sunk the family deeper into poverty. Finally, as a mechanical propelled object, the buses also requires constant maintenance, the maintenance need in turn offers employment opportunities to motor mechanics, panel beaters, spray painters, vulcanizers, and so on. The use of premium motor spirit, associate gas oil (AGO) and lubricants by the buses has helped dealers and markets of such products enjoy increase sales, quick turnover which translated into more profit and poverty reduction The Port Harcourt Children's Home on the other hand between 1999 and 2015, housed and cared for one thousand six hundred and forty eight (1,648) orphans and vulnerable children. The home which also has a total of forty-six (46) staffs out of which twenty-five are casuals, who earn daily payment from working at the home with which they provide for the economic needs of their family in trying to escape poverty. That aside, the livelihood of the permanent staffs and their families also depends on the salaries they earn by working at the home. The government spends between Twenty-seven Million Naira (N27,000.000) to Twenty-Nine million man (N29,000.000) Yearly for the feeding at the home and five million naira (N5,000.000) Per year on the education of the children at the home. The Port Harcourt Children's Home does not have a market of her own, neither does it operate a school, the money budgeted for feeding and education when put in use translate into an income for the ordinary market woman and teachers at the various schools. The vulnerable children cared for at the home are among the lucky once who has escaped infant poverty or death as a result of the care and protection provided at the home. As earlier mentioned a large chunk of the Rivers State Government social security programmes are run through the Ministry of Social Welfare, the ministry oversees the activities of the Port Harcourt Children's Home, The Remand Home, Approved schools and the Rehabilitation Centre Iriebe. Other ministries and

Social Security Programmes/Projects and Poverty Reduction in Ogba Egbema Local Government Rivers State.

Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni, formerly referred to as the Old Ahoada Local Government Area, was established in 1991 in Rivers State, Nigeria. Its administrative centre is located at Omoku. According to the 2006 Census, it has about 258,700 residents and is bordered by the states of Imo, Delta, Bayelsa, and Anambra as well as the local government areas of Ahoada West, Ahoada East, and Emohua in Rivers State. They are a part of the Igbo-speaking regions of Rivers State, which are made up of three tribes: the Ogba, which dominates the region and has 12 legislative wards, the Egbema, which has two, and the Ndoni, which has three. With roughly 12 mining/producing fields run by AGIP, Total Energies, and Shell/NPDC, along with numerous

other reserve/untapped fields, it is primarily upland and the scene of the state's largest upstream oil and gas exploration/exploitation activity since the early 1960s. It is a part of the Nigerian House of Representatives constituency known as Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni/Ahoada West. 5°20'30.01"N 6°39'20.02"E, Rivers State, Nigeria. Social and cultural life: The three ethnic groups represented in local government each have their own cultures, languages, and social customs. They hold a unique, vibrant event that includes masquerades. They host various social gatherings and amuse guests. They excel in football and wrestling. One of Rivers State's top oil and gas producers is the Ogba Egbema Ndoni Local Government Area.

The concept of social security may be viewed from many different angles, and it is clear from this that it has many different aspects because it addresses a wide range of human needs. For example, it could be viewed as a system by which a government offers basic support in the form of resources and services to its citizens who are unable to care for themselves for one reason or another. In order to prevent citizens from becoming victims of impending disaster, these amenities may include housing, physical security, technical training, health care facilities, basic education programmes, and efforts to promote equity and fairness. From the health perspective, the following health facilities has been put in place in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni, as to secure the less privileged who cannot provide their health needs and also preserved money for those that can provide for themselves but chooses to use government parastatals. Government have provided Obagi Comprehensive Health Centre, Oboburu, Ogbogu Primary Health Center , Ndoni Health Post , Ebogoro Primary Health Centre, Obor Health Post is a Public hospital, Obrikom Model Primary Health Centre, Idu-Ogba Primary Health Center, Kreigani Health Post, Amah Primary Health Center, Egbada Health post , Elieta Health post, Ikiri Health Post, Obigwe Health Post, Gbeye Hospital and Maternity ltd, Ohiauga Health Post, Erema Primary Health centre, Okposi Health Centre, Ebocha Model Primary Health center, Akabuka Primary Health Centre, Mgbede Model Primary Health Centre, Obite Primary Health centre , Okwuzi Model Primary Health Centre, Ndoni Comprehensive Health Centre, Aggah Health Post , Ase-Azaga Model Primary Health Centre, Akabta Health Post, Obiyebe Primary Health Centre, The First Foundation Clinic Limited is a Private hospital attending to the public, General Hospital Omoku, Omoku Model Primary Health Center and The Capstone Clinic which is a Private hospital. All of the aforementioned hospital and health centers are located at Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government, Rivers State for the purpose social security. (<https://thehospitalbook.com> 2022). It was a relief for the residents of Okpurukpuali Community in Rivers State's Ogba Egbema/Ndoni Local Council when the council chief started building the community's first healthcare facility in 60 years, according to Ann Godwin in *The Guardian* (2023). It was a relief for the residents of the Okpurukpuali Community in the Ogba Egbema/Ndoni Local Council in Rivers State when Onelga Local Council boss Vincent Job (centre) started building the community's first healthcare facility in 60 years. *The Guardian* learned that several pregnant women died while they travelled to the headquarters at Omoku for adequate healthcare due to the area's lack of access to healthcare facilities. During yesterday's site visit to the healthcare centre, the women expressed their excitement for the project and noted that access to healthcare was a long-standing issue. Vincent Job, Local Council head, emphasized prioritizing health care and ensuring easy access to medical treatment for women, children, and the elderly. He emphasized the importance of early illness detection and saving lives.

Nyesom Ezenwo Wike, the immediate past governor of Rivers State, promised the residents of Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (ONELGA) in Channels Incorporated Limited (2021) that the state government would continue to erect security infrastructure in the region to uphold peace. For the sake of ONELGA's overall tranquilly, he declared that the younger brother of murdered cultist Don Wanny, Mr. Oluchi Igwedibia, will soon be found together with other fleeing Don Wanny clan members. At a security meeting held in the ONELGA Council Secretariat Pavilion, Governor Wike spoke. Service commanders accompanied the governor. He made sure the dangerous cultists were located and prosecuted. "Nobody should play politics with people's safety," he said to him. In order for the people of ONELGA to recover from the destruction of the past that has hindered progress in the area, he asked the residents to cooperate with the Rivers State Government in maintaining peace in the area. The Governor also offered his condolences to the families of the deceased, as well as sympathy to the injured and a reminder that the state values their social security. He also gave his word that the Rivers State Government would pay for the injured's medical expenses and provide support for the families of the deceased. The governor specifically said that Purity Anthony, a one-year-old girl left orphaned by the Don Wanny attack, will receive training from the State Government. He said that N50 million would be provided aside for her education by the State Government. The Governor also conveyed his condolences to the relatives of the

victims, expressed compassion to the injured, and reaffirmed the importance of social security to the state. Additionally, he said that the Rivers State Government will cover the medical bills of the injured and support the families of the deceased. Purity Anthony, a 1-year-old girl made an orphan by the Don Wanny attack, will receive training from the State Government, the governor specifically stated. He said that the State Government would set aside N50 million for her education. Governments all around the world are in the business of offering social security protections for its inhabitants, which relates to supporting the elderly. The Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government is an integral part of Rivers State, and the state's social security policy for the aged, notably those who have retired from government work, includes a component called the PAY-AS-YOU-GO Contributory Pension Scheme. Agrisocial security programmes like the National Programme for Food Securities (NPFS) have been implemented in the local government under investigation. Producing enough food, in both quantity and quality, to feed every citizen throughout the year is necessary for food security. To do this, agricultural production must be improved by the use of proper knowledge of the environment, the prevailing climate, the market and how it functions, various insecticide and pesticide kinds, and crop treatment (Oriola, 2009). A follow-up to an earlier request by the Federal Government of Nigeria to the Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) for assistance under the FAO's Special Programme for Food Security to address the issues of food insecurity and poverty among rural households in Nigeria, the National Programme for Food Securities is a counterpart funded programme. Its official name at the time of its founding was Special Programme for Food Security (SPFS). The former Special Programme for Food Security, which was implemented in all of the Federation's states between 2002 and 2006, was enlarged into the National Programme for Food Security (NPFS). Following the creation of the National Medium-Term Investment Programme (NMTIP) for Nigeria in support of the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP) of the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD), the NPFS was chosen as one of the three priority projects in Nigeria.

- (1) Sustainable Development and Management of Land and Water Resources was the focus of the project.
- (2) Increasing market access and infrastructure in rural areas
- (3) Increasing household food security and income
- (4) Developing fisheries and aquaculture
- (5) and Livestock Development (World Bank Report, 2009).

The Special Programme for Food Security (SPFS) ended in 2002, but the Nigerian National Programme for Food Security (NPFS) began in 2003. The Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development in Abuja served as the program's top management committee, and the Agricultural Development Programme (ADP) authorities in the federation's states served as the state-level implementation agencies. Following the first pilot phase, the second phase began in 2007 with nine sites with the word "Special" dropped from the program's name. Each of the three senatorial districts in Rivers State had one site for the scheme. The National Programme for Food Security (NPFS) was created to carry out the following particular goals:

- (i) Helping farmers increase the production of important crops and livestock.
- (ii) Boost household incomes, profitability, and productivity. (ADP Report, 2008, p.4).
- (iii) Train and educate farmers in the efficient use of the land, water, and other resources and facilities available to produce food and generate employment on a sustainable basis. The targets are:
 - a) To improve the efficacy of research and extension services by disseminating technology and novel farming practises created by research institutes to farmers.
 - b) To assist farmers in realising their full potential for increased output and productivity, and thus revenue, on a long-term basis.
- b) To supply high-quality certified seed/seedlings and planting materials of high-yielding, disease-resistant crop types, as well as fertilisers and other pertinent inputs.

The Rivers State experience provided empirical support for the program's pilot phase. The plan intended to run five years, from 2008 to 2013 (RSMA, 2008). The stipulated eligibility criteria for NPFS activities

arising from availability of land is showcased at the following locations across Rivers State: Atali/Elingbu/Eneka (Obio/Akpor L.G.A), Idoka/Ihuaba (Ahoada West L. G. A., Opiro (Etche L.G.A.),

Oyorokoto (Adoni L.G.A.), Rumu-Ada (Emohua L.G.A.), Akabuka (Onelga L.G.A), Umuagbai (Oyigbo L.G.A.) and Okoboh (Ahoada West L.G.A).(RSMA, 2008).1506

Consequence of Social Insecurity in Ogba Egbema Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Social security reduces poverty, but social insecurity increases poverty. Some residents of Ndoni Community in Rivers State's Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area are still calculating their losses from last year's disastrous flood. People who spoke to The Tide in the village estimated their losses to be in the millions of naira. They claimed that the flood ruined their properties, including farmlands and other sources of income. According to them, the scenario has also exacerbated the area's malaria infestation. Mrs Rose Umeze told The Tide that the storm destroyed all of her property because "the water was everywhere in the community." "The flood was everywhere," she says, "and everything we suffered for was destroyed." "No food, nothing came out," he said, adding that the extent of destruction caused by the tragedy caught the neighbourhood off guard. Another resident, Ifeanyi Obueze, also spoke out, claiming that lives were lost during the disaster. "Everything has been ruined in the last two years." They predicted that it would return this year, he said. He claimed that when the water levels in the nearby rivers rise, the locals are now forced to live in fear. "The rivers are already filling up again, and the places where the water used to come from are already filled up," he said. Obieze claimed that because the flood now occurs annually, the community is already powerless. The community's food supply is unremarkable since everything will spoil once more with no palliative, just as it did last year when both plants and food died. They promised to bring something, but as of right now, nothing has materialised as they had promised. "I won't lie to you; a lot of young people and the elderly perished due to the flood everywhere. He bemoaned the lack of a hospital to care for them, the lack of medication, and the fact that we were unable to travel to Omoku for treatment since the road was closed by flooding.

The community's food supply is unremarkable since everything will spoil once more with no palliative, just as it did last year when both plants and food died. They promised to bring something, but as of right now, nothing has materialised as they had promised. "I won't lie to you; a lot of young people and the elderly perished due to the flood everywhere. He bemoaned the lack of a hospital to care for them, the lack of medication, and the fact that we were unable to travel to Omoku for treatment since the road was closed by flooding. Executive Director of LDE, Nbani Friday Barilule, noted that communities in the oil-rich Niger Delta region have suffered significant harm as a result of climate change in his remarks at a two-day Niger Delta Climate Change Conference organised by the organisation with the theme "Niger Delta and Climate Change: Imperatives for Action." Barilule noted a number of the negative effects of climate change in the area, such as the extinction of species, the degradation of aquatic life, and the degradation of farmlands. In order to create a cleaner environment, Rev. Nnimmo Bassey, Executive Director of Mother Earth Foundation, emphasised the significance of government investment in renewable energy. He also highlighted the ecocide in the Niger Delta and the fact that a bad attitude towards the environment causes more harm than good. Bassey added, "People are not secured in the flood," in reference to the government's inexperience in addressing the impacts of floods in the area. Security involves more than just arming police officers and placing roadblocks on highways; in recent years, it has actually done more environmental harm than growth. According to the Nigerian Constitution and the African Charter for Human and Peoples Rights, security should include providing a liveable environment. Bassey criticised the government for doing nothing to alleviate the effects of flooding. If the government is unable to provide alternatives, security, safety measures, relief supplies, or compensation to individuals who have been impacted over time, it has failed in its duty to warn people about impending flooding. According to government estimates, the most recent flooding killed 603 Nigerians and caused one million people to be homeless. That, in my opinion, is a tragedy that calls for action, but none has been taken thus far. Human rights advocate Celestine Akpobari also discussed flooding, saying, "By now, a government that cares about the people should have known that they will build a very big IDP camp where people will go to when the flood comes." The issue of floods should, in Akpobari's opinion, receive more attention than an oil leak, and the government should be urged to find ways to control the situation during the wet season. Nigeria recently experienced flooding that claimed 603 lives and left one million homeless.

Celestine Akpobari, a human rights lawyer, thinks the government should prioritise building sizable IDP camps over oil spill prevention.

Insecurity and Community Development

Insecurity generally disrupts development of nations and societies. Denney (2013) observed that the relationship between insecurity and underdevelopment is much stronger than the relationship between peace and development. That is, where there is conflict there is often underdevelopment. This view was shared by Dike (2013) when he asserted that lack of security of lives and property of citizens is a major hindrance to meaningful development. A climate of fear frightens domestic and foreign agencies interested in carrying out development programmes or investment and it also limits people's ability to develop economically. Similarly, Ugwu (2013) in highlighting the effect of insecurity on community development noted that many communities cannot benefit from any development project because of unresolved age-long conflicts. This is because it is difficult to mobilize members of such community to get involved in development process since workers cannot enter conflict prone communities for fear of hostility, Imobighe in Ugwu (2013) observed that: in conflict prone areas, unemployment rises, financial and banking systems become in-operative as investors have no confidence anymore and move to more secure areas. Ugwu (2008:105) further observed that: During conflicts, there is inadequate cooperation among community members, absence of outside support, destruction of completed projects, inadequate participation in community development process, difficulty in need identification, lack of fund among others which impact negatively on community development. These far reaching effects of insecurity in most cases put a halt on development in affected communities and retrogression sets in. Children and youths are more vulnerable to conflict through the indirect impact of a weak state and social system, loss of parents or caregivers and often play roles as participants in armies. As they struggle with their own identity, they watch the social fabric collapse around them. The breakdown of social structures can be detrimental to the development of children and youths in their most important years (Ugwu, 2013).

Furthermore, according to Imobighe (2003) Nigeria's security challenges have great effect on the economic growth and development in the country. This was supported by Eme and Anthony in Dantala (2014) when he summarized the effect of insecurity on development in Nigeria in the following ways:

- i. Social dislocation and population displacement.
- ii. Social tensions and new pattern of settlements which encourages Muslims/Christians or members of an ethnic group moving to Muslim/Christian dominated enclaves.
- iii. Heightens citizenship question and encourages hostility between "indigenes" and "settlers".
- iv. Dislocation and disruption of family and communal life.
- v. General atmosphere of mistrust, fear, anxiety and frenzy.
- vi. Dehumanization of women, children, and men especially in areas where rape, child abuse and neglect are used as instruments of war.
- vii. Deepening of hunger and poverty in the polity.
- viii. Atmosphere of political insecurity and instability including declining confidence in the political leadership and apprehension about the system.
- ix. Governance deficit as a result of security agencies inefficiency and corruption.
- x. Loss of man hours due to shortened working hours by banks and commercial institutions and the unprecedented loss of man hours or closure of businesses by those who work at night due to the curfew consequent on the declaration of state of emergency on some states. This has affected the informal but widespread sector of the local economy such as *suya*, *shayi*, *kosai* vendors who make out their living on day to day basis (Shettima, 2012)1507

V. Methodology

This paper adopted the exploratory survey design. Survey design was used in this study for its economy, rapid data collection and ability to understand the characteristics of the population under study (Sekaran, 2011). In addition, the survey design was deployed to collect data from a defined population in order to describe the present condition of the population using the prescribed variables. Community development programmes constituted the independent variables in this study while poverty alleviation was considered the dependent variable. According to accessible records from the National population commission, the total population of adult male and female residents based on 2006 population census is 283,294, focus

interactions was carried between some selected personalities using the multistage sampling technique. Employing a dichotomous questionnaire comprising multiple choice options and Likert type statements to collect data, simple percentage was used to analyse the collected data in order to realize the paper objectives.

VI. Discussion of Findings

It was discovered that the ONELGA community in Rivers State has three different types of community-based programmes, including initiatives to improve agriculture and increase food sufficiency, programmes to increase the educational and intellectual capacity of ONELGA residents, and initiatives to promote healthy living and lengthen people's lives. In a similar vein, the study discovers that a larger proportion of locals took part in the redevelopment of their town. Similar to this, members of the ONELGA community take an active role in numerous ways to ensure the success of programmes for community development. The planning and decision-making stages of community development projects, active membership registration, active membership contributions, voluntary donations, regular attendance at community meetings, providing training assistance to community members, providing security services by keeping watch over ONELGA community projects to prevent abuses, vandalism, etc. are just a few of the areas of participation. According to Abasiokong (1991), the rural poor are agricultural producers who have tiny holdings, low earnings, and restricted access to government services, technical help, and finance. People of this type are unable to conceptualise community development initiatives since their circumstances seem so precarious as to seriously impair their ability to subsist. Because of the negative consequences of poverty, they are unable to participate in projects for community development. Additionally, it was discovered that the residents of the ONELGA community have benefited from the successful implementation of community-based programmes. ONELGA people now apply for bank loans using their records in community development programmes as collateral, and through community programmes people can use proceeds from business to assist their family members. As an example, entrepreneurial skills have been greatly improved, which fosters a sense of belonging. People can now own and operate their own businesses thanks to the support of community programmes. As a result, there is a strong connection between community development programmes and the reduction of poverty. The results of the study also show a strong correlation between community development projects' accessibility and the state of infrastructure development.

VII. Conclusion

Based on the numerous effects of the programmes on the microeconomics of households, families, and other beneficiaries and participants during its duration, the social security programmes for children of the Rivers State government have reportedly made an important contribution to the reduction of poverty in the state. The demise of some programmes has a severe blowback effect on families and households, resulting in a significant decrease in household purchasing power. The total consequences of the Port Harcourt Children's Home activities on the lives of OVCs have rescued many children from the effects of abject poverty and provided them with a life line and a pedestal from which to see life from a different viewpoint. The cessation of these programmes not only reintroduces poverty by reducing household purchasing power, but it also removes jobs and employment opportunities from citizens.

VIII. Recommendation

This work therefore recommends as follows:

1. That the state government resurrect and sustain the free school bus programme and the free medical care programme for the benefit of citizens and the state.
2. That the state-owned syringe manufacturing enterprise be repaired to aid in the creation of jobs and the alleviation of poverty.
3. More funds should be invested in care homes and the construction of new ones in other zones.

4. Government and corporate organisations, faith-based organisations, and individuals should begin more productive community development activities to alleviate poverty in rural communities and to assist in the funding and completion of community development programmes.

5. There should be a mechanism in place to ensure that monies intended for development activities are not misappropriated but are used properly.

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